

A STUDY ON ADVERSE EFFECTS OF DRUGS DURING THE CLINICAL MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES**Khushboo****Department of Pharmacology, Jaipur college of Pharmacy, Jaipur (Raj.)****Received: 15-07-2022 / Revised: 06-08-2022 / Accepted: 25-09-2022****Corresponding author: Khushboo****Conflict of interest: Nil****Abstract**

Background: DM is one of the widely spread disorder in the world. In this disease the blood sugar level increases. The management of DM is done by several oral hypoglycemic drugs. In this study we are observing the adverse effects during the management of DM and produced due to the consumption of anti-diabetic drugs. After the completion of the study we will be able to know the outcome of the adverse effects.

Aim & Objective: To observe the adverse drug reactions of drugs during the clinical management of the diabetes to overcome them and make life easy by safe use of drugs and balanced diet.

Method: The patients were selected from O.P.D of Imperial Hospital & Research Center. Total 509 patients will be selected on the basis of different study criteria. Patient counseling process was carried out using specified forms taken them for analysis.

Observation: Individuals of age 35-75 year, both sex and different type adverse effects were selected for present study. Initially total 550 patients were taken; out of 550 patients, 41 patients had discontinued the clinical trial due to selection criteria. Finally 509 patients were included. It was found that out of 509 patients 30% were below 50yr. male, 24% were below 50yr. females, 25% were above 50yr. male & 21% were above 50yr. females. It was found that out of 509 patients 75, 76, 84 & 132 patients of them were affected due to Dryness; Hair loss, Muscular & joint pain; Irregular breathing.

Result & Conclusion: As per the anthropometric assessment showing in the table and chart, the multiple and combination therapy of drugs having multiple and highest peak of the adverse effects. The highest percentage of adverse effects were found with drugs Metformin + Glimpride + Pioglitazone. The patients with Metformin + Glimpride + Pioglitazone were suffering from all the side effects as compared to other. The highest peak of patients found of the adverse effects were found with drug Metformin + Glipizide in male below 50 year old, where as in male above 50 year old found highest peak of patients with drug Metformin + Glimpride + Pioglitazone. The minimum adverse effects were recorded with drug Metformin with minimum number of patients. The second minimum adverse effects were recorded with drug Glimpride. As per the above results we can conclude that the drug Pioglitazone having maximum adverse effects as compared to other drugs.

Keywords: Diabetes, DM, Hyperglycaemia

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INTRODUCTION

DM is one of the widely spread disorder in the world. In this disease the blood sugar level increases. The management of DM is

done by several oral hypoglycemic drugs. In this study we are observing the adverse effects during the management of DM and

produced due to the consumption of anti-diabetic drugs. After the completion of the study we will be able to know the outcome of the adverse effects. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is probably one of the oldest diseases known to man. It was first reported in Egyptian manuscript about 3000 years ago.[1]

In 1936, the distinction between type 1 and type 2 DM was clearly made.[2] Type 2 DM was first described as a component of metabolic syndrome in 1988.[3] Type 2 DM (formerly known as non-insulin dependent DM) is the most common form of DM characterized by hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, and relative insulin deficiency.[4] Type 2 DM results from interaction between genetic, environmental and behavioral risk factors.[5,6]

People living with type 2 DM are more vulnerable to various forms of both short- and long-term complications, which often lead to their premature death. This tendency of increased morbidity and mortality is seen in patients with type 2 DM because of the commonness of this type of DM, its insidious onset and late recognition, especially in resource-poor developing countries like Africa.[7]

Method & Material: The patients were selected from O.P.D of Imperial Hospital & Research Center. Total 509 patients will be selected on the basis of different study criteria. Patient counseling process was carried out using specified forms taken them for analysis.

Selection: The patients were selected from O.P.D of Imperial Hospital & Research Center. Total 509 patients will be selected out of 550 on the basis of different study criteria. The questionnaire forms were filled for the patients as sample. The

inclusion and exclusion criteria for the patients were as follow:

Inclusion Criteria: Males or females age would not less than to 35 years. Males or females age would not more than to 75 years. No limitations of physical activity

Exclusion Criteria: Severe orthopedic/cardiovascular/respiratory conditions restricting physical activity, Women who were pregnant and lactating at the time of study and Known case of HIV infection
Instrumentation and Outcome Measurement: To carry out the study following tools were used. Subjects were assessed for the following ACQ.

- Anthropometric Assessment
- Clinical Assessment
- Questionnaires

The summarized clinical assessments after the counseling and questionnaires was detailed in the tabulated form for anthropometric data of observed adverse effects as follow:

AE-1 = Dryness, AE-2 = Hair loss

AE-3 = Muscular & Joint Pain, AE-4 = Irregular breathing

OBSERVATION : Individuals of age 35-75 year, both sex and different type adverse effects were selected for present study. Initially total 550 patients were taken; out of 550 patients, 41 patients had discontinued the clinical trial due to selection criteria. Finally 509 patients were included. It was found that out of 509 patients 30% were below 50yr. male, 24% were below 50yr. females, 25% were above 50yr. male & 21% were above 50yr. females. It was found that out of 509 patients 75, 76, 84 & 132 patients of them were affected due to Dryness; Hair loss, Muscular & joint pain; Irregular breathing.

Table1: Anamnetic, Anthropometric Parameters of participants

DRUG USED	B50M-AE-1	B50M-AE-2	B50M-AE-3	B50M-AE-4	A50M-AE-1	A50M-AE-2	A50M-AE-3	A50M-AE-4	B50F-AE-1	B50F-AE-2	B50F-AE-3	B50F-AE-4	A50F-AE-1	A50F-AE-2	A50F-AE-3	A50F-AE-4
METFORMIN+VOGLIBOSE	15	16	21	31	14	7	20	20	17	6	18	27	7	1	19	17
GLIMPRIDE	0	2	2	6	0	0	0	4	5	0	0	13	1	1	1	6
METFORMIN+GLIPIZIDE	17	22	18	35	8	6	18	17	19	6	14	30	9	6	25	30
VIDAGLIPTIN+METFORMIN	11	10	7	16	6	6	9	11	5	2	6	12	5	3	19	20
METFORMIN+GLIMPRIDE+PIOGLITAZONE	10	10	10	10	26	26	26	26	5	5	5	5	3	3	3	3
METFORMIN	1	0	1	4	3	3	3	3	3	0	0	8	1	0	1	0
GLIMPRIDE+METFORMIN	21	16	25	30	11	12	22	24	15	4	7	19	2	1	14	14

Figure 1: Upper confidential of different adverse effects

RESULT & CONCLUSION

As per the anthropometric assessment showing in the table and chart, the multiple and combination therapy of drugs having multiple and highest peak of the adverse effects. The highest percentage of adverse effects were found with drugs Metformin + Glimpride + Pioglitazone. The patients with Metformin + Glimpride + Pioglitazone were suffering from all the side effects as compared to other. The highest peak of patients found of the adverse effects were found with drug Metformin + Glipizide in male below 50 year old, where as in male above 50 year old found highest peak of patients with drug Metformin + Glimpride + Pioglitazone. The minimum adverse effects were recorded with drug Metformin with minimum number of patients. The second minimum adverse effects were recorded with drug Glimpride. As per the above results we can conclude that the drug Pioglitazone having maximum adverse effects as compared to other drugs.

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